

OSCAR Well-being Mentoring Program

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What is Well-being mentoring?

Well-being mentoring is a process based on trust, confidentiality and mutual respect, in which the mentee can feel safe to self-reflect and explore new ways to deal with specific challenges, regarding his/her life as a researcher, that have an impact on his/her well-being. This growing process involves the guidance and help of the mentor, someone who knows the challenges of working in academia, and can use their previous experience in order to support the mentee's professional and personal development. Even though the well-being mentorship is a supportive relationship, it is not psychotherapy.

Purpose & Goals

The main purpose and goal of the OSCAR well-being mentoring program is to support mental health, and the developing of well-being competencies and skills.

Based on the OSCAR well-being framework, the well-being skills are: (1) Finding Meaning in Life, (2) Finding Meaning at Work, (3) Awareness of Well-being, (4) Recognizing and Understanding Emotions, (5) Emotion Regulation, (6) Stress Management, (7) Setting goals, (8) Psychological Resilience, (9) Accountability, (10) Finding a Work-Life Balance, (11) Strengthening Social Relationships, (12) Assertive Communication, (13) Interpersonal and Social Empathy, (14) Dealing with Perfectionism, (15) Promoting Self-Kindness, and (16) Increasing Self-Confidence.

How does the user get enrolled into the mentoring program?

The user can request a mentor through two different ways:

- 1) While learning a skill, the learning user can request a mentor in order to improve his/her learning process.
- 2) The user can request a mentor even without starting any skill's training.

The user/learner will indicate the challenge or skill they want to focus on during the mentoring, and how long they believe they are committed to improve it. The user/learner will be made aware through a disclaimer that the mentoring relationship is not a therapy process and will also learn how to identify the warning signs of mental illness and what to do in those cases (i.e. find professional help).

In both cases, the mentor should direct the mentee to relevant content in eDoer, indicating personalized resources that match the mentee's learning preferences, and that will support the problem/challenge resolution.

Types of well-being mentoring:

- 1) Short-term mentoring: when the mentee is looking for some specific, and momentary guidance regarding the learning of a specific skill or topic, with only a few sessions needed to achieve this goal (for one to three months).
- 2) Long-term mentoring: when the mentee is looking for a relationship that will last for an extended period, in order to successfully achieve his/her goals (at least one communication per two months, for at least one year).

The mentor's and mentee's needs, willingness, and availability will help clarify if the mentoring relationship should be defined as short or long term.

In both types of mentoring, the mentor will have a maximum of two mentees simultaneously. Additionally, both mentor and mentee will give feedback on each other at the end of the mentoring relationship (e.g., through a multiple choice question that uses different emojis, and an open and optional space to add commentaries).

Role of the mentor

A good mentor is someone who is interested in helping and guiding mentees in increasing their well-being, by actively listening to their difficulties, and by sharing new and more helpful ways to deal with the specific challenge.

Mentors will create a structured dialogue and use their acquired knowledge, both from personal experience and from the OSCAR 'mentorship for well-being' training course, in order to best guide the mentee. Therefore, mentors are expected to have gone through similar challenges, or at least to have seen other people (colleagues, etc.) go through similar challenges.

The selection criteria for the mentors are:

- Mentors need to have finished a PhD or to have completed 4 to 5 years of scientific research, even if at the moment he/she works outside of academia.
- Mentors need to complete a course of 'mentorship for well-being' created by OSCAR (ideally, their learning should be assessed).
- Mentors need to agree with ethical principles regarding the mentorship process.

The Matching process

The idea is to empower autonomy and encourage more engagement from the mentee in the matching process. Additionally we want to test the worst case scenario: how can we automate the matching process (no human decision from OSCAR), and still keep it ethical and helpful?

In order to accomplish our objectives, the matching process can either consist of a self-matching type, where the mentee selects the mentor, or an hybrid matching type, where both mentor and mentee would answer a set of selected questions, and from those answers the system would be able to create a pool of mentors for the mentee to choose from. The hybrid matching type is used by mentoring software, as:

<https://chronus.com>

<https://www.guider-ai.com>

The matching system works as follows:

- 1) Matching between mentors and mentees is based on the skills mentees aim to develop and mentors have in their curriculum;
- 2) The mentee can also include in their Mentor Selection mentors' interests, areas of expertise, nationality, age and gender.

The matching journey works as follows:

- 1st: the mentee will select the skill they want to add to their curriculum. Skills will be presented with a brief description and the potential challenges where these can be applied.
- 2nd: the system will present the list of mentors that have the knowledge in the skills picked by the mentee as well as other variables the mentee included in the selection (interests, areas of expertise, nationality, age, gender).
- 3rd: After this the system will show the available mentors based on the chosen criteria. The system will show a profile of the potential mentors (photo, name, bio), and their preferred means to communicate throughout the mentorship (e.g., email, videocall, chat). The mentee will select their preferred mentor.
- 4th: The mentor will receive the request of the mentee and will decide whether or not he/she wants to start the process.
- 5th: The mentor will send a message through the platform with the suggestion to start the mentorship.